

Research Article

Management Functions and Democratic Member Control in Rwanda: A Case of Selected Agri-Business Cooperatives of Kamonyi District

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Abstract

This study evaluated the management functions and Democratic Member Control of Agri-Business Cooperative in Rwanda. Case studies were Selected Agri-Business Cooperatives of Kamonyi District. The issue is that many cooperatives in Rwanda struggle to stay active for long. It was assumed that indicators of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) mutually do not affect significantly democratic member control of Agri-Business Cooperatives in Rwanda. The study was conducted quantitatively. It used descriptive survey research design. Population of the study was 2856 members of selected cooperatives in Kamonyi District (COARIFIKA, Impabaruta and Indatwa). The study used simple random sampling technics to respond to the questionnaire. The researcher gave questionnaire and collected answers of them from 309 respondents. Data was processed through mean and standard deviations that were used in assessing the level of management functions and democratic member control. Hypothesis was tested by using multiple linear regression. Findings shows different critical performances of cooperative managers such as poor stimulation of cooperative members to higher levels of work and better quality of work. Based on the F-test which is 289.741 and significant at .000, management functions indicators jointly have positive and significant effect on Democratic Member Control. Therefore, there is a significant effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control.

Keywords: Management function, Cooperative performance, Democratic Member Control.

Introduction

The cooperative is defined as an association aimed to achieve certain objectives for the members within the context of markets. The importance of the cooperative derives from generating well-being for participant cooperators that wouldn't exist if ever each member works alone (Dijk *et al.*, 2019). With a membership of over three million people, Rwanda's cooperative movement is a strong vehicle for development and economic empowerment especially among the disadvantaged groups like women, youth and PWDs. However, many cooperatives struggle to stay operational given the above challenges, according to Dr. Augustin Katararwa, the chairperson of the National Cooperative Confederation Rwanda (NCCR). Katararwa said these challenges require urgent interventions to ensure that "coops are run professionally". "In addition, those who head cooperatives should be honest, and promote good governance and accountability practices that ensure transparency and good management," he said (The New Times, 2018). According to The New Times (2018), many agri-business cooperatives in Rwanda are facing huge challenges including mismanagement and other governance issues such as fraud and misuse of property, as well as a lack of sustainable markets and the ability to operate efficiently. Rwanda has experienced a large number of cooperative failures in rural areas. In addition, some of the members side-sell produce, affecting the performance and cash flow of the cooperatives in the country (The New Times, 2018). This study seeks to investigate the effect of Management Functions on Democratic Member Control of Agri-Business Cooperative in Rwanda with case study of COARIFIKA, Impabaruta and Indatwa located in Kamonyi District.

Objectives and Hypothesis of the Study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the effect of management functions on cooperative Performance in Rwanda. Specifically the objective is to examine effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control in Rwanda agri-business

cooperatives. The researcher assumes that there is no significant effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control in Rwanda agri-business cooperative.

Literature

Management is the process of achieving cooperative mission, strategies, goals, and objectives through the use of people, money, other physical resources, and data. The people in a cooperative are employees and members. The money used in a cooperative is any sort of financial resource or capital that the cooperative uses toward achieving anticipated cooperative goals. The other things in a cooperative include physical resources, such as equipment, computers, desks, chairs, tables, lamps, and even the building where the cooperative resides. The data or knowledge in a cooperative are any sort of information, such as databases or archives that are used by the cooperative to help accomplish desired cooperative goals (Miles, 2012). According to David (2011), the functions of management consist of five basic activities: planning, organizing, motivating, staffing, and controlling.

Planning

Planning involves all managerial activities related to get ready for the future. Planning includes forecasting, setting objectives, developing strategies, developing policies and setting goals (David, 2011). Planning is an intellectual activity. It is the process by which managers establish goals and specify how these goals are to be attained. Plans have two basic components: outcome or goal statements and action statements. Outcome or goal statements represent the end state or the targets and outcomes managers hope to attain. Action statements reflect the means by which organizations move forward to attain their goals (OpenStax, 2019).

Organizing

Organizing refers to all managerial actions that are done through structures, tasks and authorities relationships. Organizing considers organizational design, job specialization, job descriptions, job specifications, and span of control, unity of command, coordination, job design, and job analysis (David, 2011). David (2011) confirms that the organizing function of management consists of three consecutive activities: transforming tasks into jobs (work specialization), combining jobs to form sections (departmentalization), and entrusting authority. Breaking down tasks into jobs requires the setting of job descriptions and job specifications. These tools clarify for both managers and employees what particular jobs entail. According to OpenStax (2019) an organizational structure is a system that links activities that occur within a work. Activities to be done are indicated by the structure. Structure shows how their work supports other employees, and how these work activities satisfy the organization mission. An organizational design is the process of establishing organizational structure to address the needs of an organization.

Coordination

The practice by which a manager harmonizes the activities of different divisions/branches is known as coordination. Coordination is the power that brings together all the other functions of management. It binds all activities such as purchase, production, sales, and finance to confirm the steadiness of the Organization. The process of coordinating the activities of an organization starts at the planning phase itself. The process of coordination ensures the orderly arrangement of individual and group efforts to make unity of actions towards the achievement of common objectives. Thus coordination includes synchronization of the diverse actions or efforts of the several units of an organization. This requires financial resources, quality, time and series of efforts so that planned objectives be achieved well (Mohd *et al.*, 2021).

Directing and Controlling

Leadership is the lifting up of the person's vision to higher standards, the nurturing of a person's performance to a higher standard, the building of a person's character beyond its ordinary boundaries (David, 2011). Motivating involves efforts concentrating toward modelling human behavior. Specific topics include leadership, communication, work groups, behavior modification, and delegation of authority, job enrichment, job satisfaction, needs fulfillment, organizational change, employee morale, and managerial morale (David, 2011). According to David (2011), controlling ensures that actual performance are consistent with planned performance. Key areas of concern include quality control, financial control, sales control, inventory control, and expense control, analysis of variances, rewards, and sanctions.

Democratic Member Control

Cooperative is known as a shield between cooperative members and the market. This shield must serve two objectives. The main objective is to assist the interests of members individually; the secondary objective is to

effectively operate the cooperative. The intention of the cooperative is to facilitate transactions between cooperative members and the market (Dijk *et al.*, 2019). The cooperative activities in question must connect activities that are important to the members' cooperative. The advantage for the members should be observable within the cooperative, and it should also be evident within the members' households. Thus, the cooperative firm is an example of the enterprise whose being is greater than the sum of its parts (Dijk *et al.*, 2019).

Methodology

This research used descriptive Survey Research design. Under this research design the procedure of quantitative information was gathered through questionnaires. Population of the study 2856 members of three cooperatives which are: Indatwa, COARIFIKA and Impabaruta of Kamonyi District. By using simple random sampling the researcher gave questionnaire to 339 (Coop members). The respondents were given questionnaire built on four-point scale ranging from 1 to 4 (strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree). The distributed questionnaire gathered all information as per its content, with aim to found out whether there is any effect of management functions on cooperative performance. Adapted questionnaire in English and Kinyarwanda was distributed to the respondents for the achievement of the study objective. 309 members responded to the questionnaire. Data was collected within the first 2 weeks of September 2022.

After collecting all necessary data through questionnaires distributed to the respondents, the researchers treated all gathered data presented in the form of tables. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to describe the level of perception of respondents of all independent variable indicators and indicator of dependent variable, while inferential statistics (multiple linear regression) was used to test hypothesis of the study. An item which had a mean between 1.00 and 1.99 was considered as a weak mean. An item which had a mean between 2.00 to 2.99 was considered as a moderate mean.

An item which had a mean between 3.00 and 4.00 was considered as a strong mean. A standard deviation less or equal to 0.5 indicated the same perception of respondent's around the mean, while a standard deviation greater or equal to 0.5 indicated different perception of respondent's around the mean.

- ✓ X= Management Function (MF)
- ✓ $X = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5)$ where
- ✓ $X_1 =$ Planning (PLG)
- ✓ $X_2 =$ Organizing (ORG)
- ✓ $X_3 =$ Coordinating (CDT)
- ✓ $X_4 =$ Directing (DIR)
- ✓ $X_5 =$ Controlling (CON) determinate.

Multiple Regression Model

- ✓ And Y= Dependent variable
- ✓ Y= Democratic Member Control (DMC)

✓ $Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5)$

Based on these variables, the following functional relationship is developed to guide econometric models that was used in testing the hypothesis.

✓ $Y = F(X)$

✓ $DMC = F(PLG, ORG, CDT, DIR, CON)$ Function.

Model Evaluation

There was test of multicollinearity, normality and test of auto correlation to see if the results are not biased before inference is made.

$DMC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PLG + \beta_2 ORG + \beta_3 CDT + \beta_4 DIR + \beta_5 CON + \mu$ Model

Perceptions of Respondents on Management Functions

This section presents perceptions of respondents on management functions within their cooperatives. The variable analyzed under this section are planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling. Questionnaire was responded by 309 respondents.

Perception of Respondent on Planning

Respondents were asked to indicate their perception on the function of *planning* within their cooperatives. Table 1 presents mean and standard deviation (δ) of findings as follows:

Table 1. Perception of Respondents on Planning.

Items Assessed	Mean	(δ)
Capacity of managers to regularly analyze well the current situation of the cooperative.	2.94	0.54
Capacity of managers in anticipating the future.	2.89	0.76
Capacity of managers to regularly determine well the organizational objectives.	3.06	0.73
Capacity of managers to decide well necessary alternative strategies to be prioritized.	3.06	0.64
Overall mean of planning	2.99	
Source: Primary data (2022)		

Findings shows that the capacity of cooperative management to regularly analyze the current situation of the cooperative is perceived by respondents with a moderate mean (2.94) with heterogeneity of perceptions of respondents around that mean ($\delta = 0.54$). Capacity of managers in anticipating the future was moderately perceived by respondents with a mean of 2.89 but with different perception around that mean as is indicated by a standard deviation of 0.76. Capacity of managers to regularly determine well the organizational objectives and capacity of managers to decide well necessary alternative strategies to be prioritized were both perceived by a strong mean of 3.06 but with heterogeneity of perceptions of respondents around that mean ($\delta = 0.73$ and $\delta = 0.64$ respectively). The overall mean for planning within agri-business cooperative results 2.99 which is moderate mean. This mean that, planning within cooperatives is not performed well enough. The implication is that when there is no good planning, expected results also, cannot be reached. Thus members of the cooperative cannot experience good results from what they are doing.

Perception of Respondent on Organizing

Respondents were asked to indicate their respondent on organizing as second management function within their respective cooperatives. Table 2 presents results of perception of respondents on organizing.

Table 2 represents findings on *organizing* which is second management function. Having always organized activities was perceived with a moderate mean 2.83 with different dispersion of perception of respondents around that mean as evidenced by a standard deviation of 0.79. Having management staff that implement well his task, is viewed by respondents as weak (2.99) and this weakness is confirmed by a standard deviation (0.41) that shows homogeneity of perception of respondents around that mean. Having article of association which is already written well and known by all cooperative members was also perceived with a moderate mean 2.83 with different dispersion of perception of respondents around that mean as evidenced by a standard deviation of 1.05. Implementing regularly and well article of association was also perceived with a moderate mean 2.60 with different dispersion of perception of respondents around that mean as

evidenced by a standard deviation of 1.04. Therefore, all these are obviously weaknesses cooperative have, thus there is a need of taking an action.

Having managers and staff who know well their tasks, delegating well power and authority to staff according to their position, preparing and submitting reports and communicate to the appropriate staff according to cooperative structure, are all strongly perceived by respondents (members of cooperatives) but this strength still is little almost to fall into moderate perception (3.17; 3.06 and 3.06 respectively). This strength is not also recognized by all members since standards deviation of all these three items show a different dispersion of perception of respondents around their means (0.62; 0.73 and 0.73 respectively). The overall mean of organizing function result a moderate mean (2.93). These indicate the weakness in organizing of cooperative operations and planning. As recommendation, management for cooperatives should know that no performance or no production, no growth can be reached without organizing activities of a cooperative.

Table 2. Perception of Respondents on Organizing.

Items Assessed	Mean	(δ)
Having always organized activities.	2.83	0.79
Having managers and staff who know well their task.	3.17	0.62
Having management staff that implements well his task.	2.99	0.41
Delegating well power and authority to staff according to their position.	3.06	0.73
Having article of association which is already written well and known by all cooperative members.	2.83	1.05
Implementing regularly and well article of association.	2.60	1.04
Preparing and submitting reports and communicate to the appropriate staff according to cooperative structure.	3.06	0.73
Overall mean of organizing	2.93	
Source: Primary data (2022)		

Perception of Respondents on Directing

Table 3 presents findings on directing and its interpretation.

Table 3. Perception of Respondents on Directing.

Items Assessed	Mean	(δ)
Having cooperative leaders that stimulate cooperative members to higher levels of work and better quality.	2.79	0.54
Having cooperative leaders who motivate enough all members of the cooperative to remain members and work hard.	3.14	0.70
Having managers of cooperative who clarify and synthesize various ideas in an effort to tie together the work of the members.	3.04	0.65
Having managers who orient well members towards achievement of cooperative goals.	3.05	0.58
Having cooperative managers that offers information, viewpoints and suggestions well, about the cooperative problem or tasks to cooperative members.	2.95	0.91
Overall mean of directing	2.99	
Source: Primary data (2022)		

Table 3 present findings on the function of directing and it interpretation. The items that assessed having cooperative leaders that stimulate cooperative members to higher levels of work and better quality and having cooperative managers that offers information, viewpoints and suggestions well, about the cooperative problem or tasks to cooperative members were all viewed by respondents with a moderate mean (2.79 and 2.95 respectively) which means all these two element are not performed well by cooperative managers. But, their standard deviation (0.54 and 0.91 respectively) shows a dispersion of perception or respondents around those means.

Having cooperative leaders who motivate enough all members of the cooperative to remain members and work hard, having managers of cooperative who clarify and synthesize various ideas in an effort to tie together the work of the members, having managers who orient well members towards achievement of cooperative goals were all strongly perceived by members of cooperatives. But this perceived strength is

little since it is very near moderate perception (means are 3.14; 3.04; 3.05 respectively) and standard deviation confirms the different views of respondents around those mean (standard deviations are: 0.70; 0.65 and 0.58). The overall mean results 2.99, is perceived as moderate mean. This indicates that respondents are not fully satisfied by the way cooperatives are directed. As recommendation cooperative management need to direct cooperative activities well enough.

Perception of Respondents on Controlling

Respondents indicate their perception on Controlling. 309 respondents were participated to respond on this management function questions. Table 4 present findings and it interpretations.

Table 4. Perception of Respondents on Controlling.

Items Assessed	Mean	(δ)
Ability of cooperative managers in determining necessary area to be controlled.	2.95	0.76
Ability of cooperative managers of establishing guidelines for controls.	2.76	0.55
Measuring well level of performance during controls.	2.94	0.80
Recognizing well positive performances during controls.	2.71	0.66
Taking well necessary corrective actions on where deviations are found.	2.77	0.65
Adjusting well standards or measures of performance when it is necessary.	2.59	0.60
Overall mean of controlling	2.79	
Source: Primary data (2022)		

All items assed under controlling (ability of cooperative managers in determining necessary area to be controlled, ability of cooperative managers of establishing guidelines for controls, measuring well level of performance during controls, recognizing well positive performances during controls, taking well necessary corrective actions on where deviations are found and adjusting well standards or measures of performance when it is necessary) were all moderately perceived by all respondents with a mean ranging from 2.59 to 2.95. This means that cooperatives have no enough controls though standard deviation of every item assessed shows different dispersion of perceptions around those means. The overall mean of controlling is 2.79. This is supposed to be a daily exercise which could help in monitoring how all planned activities are implemented.

Test Null Hypothesis (H0)

Objective of the study is to assess if management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) affect significantly democratic Member Control in Rwanda Agri-Cooperatives. Researchers assumes that Management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) do not significantly affect democratic member control in Rwanda Cooperatives.

Table 5. Model Summary.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
	.909 ^a	.827	.824	.27490	1.830
a. Predictors: (Constant), Controlling, Coordinating, Planning, Organizing and Directing.					
b. Dependent Variable: Democratic Member Control.					
Source: Primary Data, 2022					

From this table 5, the results indicates that adjusted R² is 0.824, which represent 82.4% of the effect of management functions on Democratic Member Control 0.176, which represent 17.6% are other effect that Democratic Member Control receives from other variables that are not included in the model.

Table 6. ANOVA.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	109.480	5	21.896	289.741	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.898	303	.076		
	Total	132.378	308			
a. Dependent Variable: Democratic Member Control.						
b. Predictors: (Constant) Controlling, Coordinating, Planning, Organizing and Directing.						
Source: Primary, Data, 2022						

Based on the F-test which is 289.741 and significant at .000 management functions indicators jointly (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) have positive and significant effect on Democratic Member Control. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control is rejected. Therefore there is a significant effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control.

Table 7. Coefficient.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-0.927	.116		-8.014	.000
Planning	.343	.047	.286	7.246	.000
Organizing	-.085	.055	-.083	-1.550	.122
Coordinating	.555	.052	.436	10.650	.000
Directing	.249	.069	.198	3.615	.000
Controlling	.287	.060	.217	4.810	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Democratic Member Control.					
b. Source: Primary Data, 2022					

Table 7 indicates that planning has positive and significant effect on democratic member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative ($\beta_1 = .286$; $t = 7.246$, $sig. = 0.000$). This indicates that 1 unit change in planning leads to .286 unit change in Democratic Member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperatives. Coordinating has positive and significant effect on democratic member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative ($\beta_1 = .436$; $t = 10.650$, $sig. = 0.000$). This indicates that 1 unit change in coordinating leads to .436 unit change in Democratic Member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperatives. Directing has positive and significant effect on democratic member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative ($\beta_1 = .198$; $t = 3.615$, $sig. = 0.000$). This indicates that 1 unit change in directing leads to .198 unit change in Democratic Member Control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperatives. Controlling has positive and significant effect on democratic member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative ($\beta_1 = .217$; $t = 4.810$, $sig. = 0.000$). This indicates that 1 unit change in controlling leads to .217 unit change in Democratic Member control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperatives. Table 7 indicate that Organizing has negative but not significant effect on Democratic Member Control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperatives ($\beta_2 = -.083$; $t = -1.550$, $sig. = .122$). This indicates that 1 unit change in controlling leads to -.083 unit decrease in Democratic Member Control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative. The following regression equation was obtained:

$$DMC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PLG + \beta_2 ORG + \beta_3 CDT + \beta_4 DIR + \beta_5 CON + \mu \text{ Model 1}$$

$$DMC = -0.927 + .286 PLG - .083 ORG + .436 CDT + .198 DIR + .217 CON + .116$$

Conclusion

The F-test (289.741) is significant at .000. Therefore there is a significant effect of management functions (planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and controlling) on Democratic Member Control in Rwanda Agri-Business Cooperative.

Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to management of cooperatives:

- 1) It was found out that cooperative managers have little capacity of analyzing well the current situation of the cooperative and anticipate well the future. Thus, funders and managers of cooperatives should act and see how capacity of managers of analyzing well the current situation of the cooperative can be increased and then anticipate the future.
- 2) It was found out that cooperative managers have little capacity of organizing well activities of cooperatives and management staff do not implement well his task. Thus, funders and managers of cooperatives should act and see how they can have enough capacity of organizing well their activities and each one perform his own task well and at time.
- 3) Cooperatives do not have a well-known article of association and its implementation does not satisfy members. Managers of cooperatives should prepare well their cooperative article of association and explain well its contents to all members either in the regular general assembly or other meeting. And every article of association should be well implemented.
- 4) Cooperative leaders do not stimulate cooperative members to higher levels of work and better quality of work. And targets of small groups of cooperative members are not well monitored by leaders. Thus

cooperative managers should motivate their members to higher levels of work and better quality of work and monitor well their targets of their small groups. Trainings are also needed to teach cooperative managers how to motivate members towards better quality of work.

- 5) It was found out that cooperative managers do not offer well information and viewpoints to cooperative members. Thus, cooperative managers should communicate well and enough information and viewpoints of problems and challenges that cooperatives are facing daily to cooperative members
- 6) Cooperative managers do not have enough ability of determining necessary area to be controlled, of establishing guidelines for controls, of measuring level of performance during controls, of recognizing positive performances during controls, of taking well necessary corrective actions on where deviations are found and adjusting well standards or measures of performance when it is necessary. Thus, funders and managers of cooperatives should act and see how capacity of managers in determining necessary area to be controlled, in establishing guidelines for controls, in measuring level of performance during controls, in recognizing positive performances during controls, in taking well necessary corrective actions on where deviations are found and in adjusting well standards or measures of performance when it is necessary can be obtained.
- 7) Other researchers should study other variables that were not included in this study (represented by 17.6%) that affect Democratic Member Control.

Declarations

We, Bwiza Gisele and Butera Edison, certify that this work "Management Functions and Democratic Member Control in Rwanda: A Case of Selected Agri-Business Cooperatives of Kamonyi District" is the proper original work of Bwiza Gisele done under Butera's co-supervision, in partial fulfillment of the requirement of Master's Degree of Business Administration with a major of Management. It hasn't been presented nor will be presented to any other University for a similar or any other degree award. It contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in our names, in any university or other tertiary institution and, to the best of our knowledge and belief, this work contains no material previously published or written by another person, except where due reference has been made in the text.

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Conflict of Interest: The research was conducted with ethical values and rules governing the conduct of research especially in areas of respondents' openness, personality, perception, privacy, and crediting scholars when and where due. The sourced data used for research purpose only; there was no harm or injury to any person, organization and sector in course of conducting this research and the interpretations was highly guided by choice of words to reflect objective opinion. During data processing and analysis, there was no tendency of data manipulation or falsification and the interpretation is objective in order to reflect the reality. In this research study, the investigation was done in harmonization between the researchers and the organization and the conclusion was based on the perceptions of employees on the studied variables. No any conflict of interest occurred in this research.

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